

ERROR ANALYSIS OF DESCRIPTIVE COMPOSITIONS OF TVL-ALGCIT STUDENTS: BASIS FOR PROPOSED ENGLISH REMEDIAL PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the specific patterns of grammatical errors in Grade 11 Technical Vocational Livelihood Track Senior High School students' descriptive writing and translated these findings into evidence-based curriculum interventions using Corder's Error Analysis Framework. By integrating the Surface Strategy Taxonomy and the Linguistic Category framework within an Input–Process–Output (IPO) analytical model, the study moved beyond merely identifying learners' grammatical difficulties and generated insights that informed instructional and curriculum improvement. The findings served as the empirical basis for revising the school's English Enrichment Program to enhance students' grammatical proficiency and communicative competence. Results indicated that, under the surface strategy taxonomy, substitution errors occurred most frequently, followed by omission, addition, and permutation. In terms of linguistic category errors, punctuation errors ranked highest, followed by subject–verb agreement errors, capitalization errors, run-on sentences, and sentence fragments. These findings suggest persistent challenges in learners' mastery of fundamental grammatical conventions in written English. Based on these results, a revised Enrichment Program for Students was developed, incorporating targeted lessons, instructional strategies, performance-based assessments, and clearly defined learning outcomes intended to address the most recurrent error patterns identified in the analysis. This study is therefore expected to contribute to the improvement of the current enrichment classes held for TVL Senior High School students. It is also recommended that future researchers conduct a similar study using a broader group of participants such as those in the Academic Track.

Keywords: *error analysis, linguistic errors, surface strategy taxonomy*

INTRODUCTION

The written outputs of the Technical Vocational Livelihood students at a private senior high school in the Philippines have continued to reflect persistent grammatical and mechanical shortcomings despite the institution of pre-enrollment enrichment lessons. Writing, after all, requires not just assembling sentences but organizing ideas in coherent, cohesive, and grammatically precise ways so that readers easily grasp the intended meaning. Thus, this study aims to generate localized empirical data and inform instructional design for this specific cohort. Conducting this study is in consonance with meeting the United Nations' fourth Sustainable Development Goal, namely "Ensure inclusive and equitable education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all". Identifying the grammatical errors made by students will not only help them improve their writing skills but also help English teachers determine what to focus on during the enrichment program that incoming TVL-ALGCIT students will undergo beforehand.

Conducting this study is, therefore, essential not only to pinpoint the dominant grammatical error types among TVL-ALGCIT students, but also to refine enrichment curricula, enhance writing pedagogy, and elevate communicative competence in this under-researched group. The research advances two central arguments: (1) that a diagnostic understanding of error patterns is imperative to tailor effective grammar instruction, and (2) that findings from this population will contribute theoretical and practical value to the field of English writing research. Its importance lies in strengthening English teachers' capacity to support TVL students, improving writing instruction at the senior high school level, and filling a significant gap in the Philippine error analysis literature.

In parallel to the surface taxonomy, the study employs the Linguistic Category Classification, which groups errors by the specific component of the linguistic system affected. Analyzing learners' linguistic errors can inform educators what their learners need to master the grammar of the target language. Studying these errors informs educators about their learners' fossilized habits and can guide them in identifying and correcting them (Samad, 2022). Empirical studies consistently validate the use of linguistic error classification for improving writing pedagogy. Nguyen et al (2021) and Pham & Vu (2021) reported that morphological and syntactic errors were dominant among Vietnamese university students, while Matwangsang et al. (2025) found that syntactic and lexical errors were prevalent in Thai EFL learners' writing. In Bangladesh, Khan (2022) noted that the most recurring problems involved the misuse of tense and prepositions. In the Philippines, Omongos and Villarin (2023) documented that senior high school students' essays contained numerous lexical and grammatical inaccuracies that impeded clarity. These findings underscore the pedagogical relevance of linguistic categorization as a tool for designing focused interventions.

The present study integrates both the Surface Strategy Taxonomy and the Linguistic Category Classification to produce a comprehensive picture of the grammatical difficulties faced by TVL-ALGCIT students. By combining these two perspectives, the study can reveal both the forms of errors and the linguistic domains in which they occur, making the findings more actionable for teachers revising enrichment curricula.

This investigation followed the Input–Process–Output (IPO) framework. The input consists of descriptive compositions written by Grade 11 TVL-ALGCIT students. These compositions serve as the empirical basis for identifying grammatical errors. The process involves analyzing these writing samples using the integrated Surface Strategy and Linguistic Category frameworks. Each identified error will be coded, classified, and tabulated to determine frequency and dominance patterns. This mirrors the methods used by Setiyorini et al. (2020) and Susilowati et al (2024), whose studies confirmed that systematic error categorization yields meaningful pedagogical insights. The output will be a set of empirically grounded instructional recommendations—targeted grammar modules, writing workshops, and feedback strategies designed to reduce recurring errors and improve writing accuracy.

The purpose of this study is to identify the grammar errors made by TVL senior high school students in a university in Cagayan de Oro in their written compositions. This will help the school revise an English Enrichment Program that the Enrichment teachers can use during the pre-admission phase for incoming TVL Grade 11 students. This study, therefore, aims to use Corder’s (1967) Error Analysis to identify students’ errors in omission, substitution, addition, permutation, subject-verb agreement, sentence fragments, run-on sentences, capitalization, and punctuation. After which, a revised enrichment program will be made.

Research Questions

Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the most frequent error types found in the narrative-descriptive compositions of the TVL-ALGCIT students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Omission;
 - 1.2 Substitution;
 - 1.3 Addition;
 - 1.4 Permutation; and
 - 1.5 Linguistic Errors
 - 1.5.1 subject-verb agreement
 - 1.5.2 sentence fragment
 - 1.5.3 run-on sentences
 - 1.5.4 capitalization
 - 1.5.5 punctuation?
2. Based on the findings of the study, what revised enrichment program can be recommended?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design with error analysis was used to systematically identify, classify, and describe errors found in learners’ language production. Descriptive research aims to present the characteristics of a phenomenon as it naturally occurs without

manipulating variables (Creswell 2018). This approach is appropriate for the present study because it allows the researcher to analyze the participants' written compositions, classify the grammatical errors, and determine their frequency and distribution to better understand learners' writing difficulties.

Participants of the study and sampling procedure

The study made use of purposive sampling. This approach was chosen to ensure that the Grade 11 students of the TVL-ALGCIT were represented fairly. Specifically, the study made use of criterion purposive sampling as it ensured that all the participants met the same criteria of being a current Grade 11 TVL ALGCIT student of the chosen school. Additionally, this group of students exhibited the most errors in grammar in their written compositions; such that they had been chosen to be the participants for this study. The participants included in the study were those who met the following inclusion criteria: (1) they were officially enrolled as Grade 11 students under the TVL-ALGCIT Track, and (2) they were willing to participate voluntarily in the study. These criteria ensured that all participants were qualified members of the target group and had given their consent to be part of the research. Students who did not express willingness to participate were excluded from the study to ensure ethical compliance and the voluntary nature of participation.

Research instrument

The study utilized a researcher-designed writing task as the research instrument. The instrument provided specific instructions, including the topic for the paragraph which was "The Soundtrack of my Life", the number of sentences to be written, and the allotted time for writing. After the allotted time, the written compositions were collected in their original form without any corrections to preserve the authenticity of the students' language use.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What are the most frequent error types found in the narrative-descriptive compositions of the TVL-ALGCIT students in terms of:

- 1.1 Omission;**
- 1.2 Substitution;**
- 1.3 Addition;**
- 1.4 Permutation; and**
- 1.5 Linguistic Errors**
 - 1.5.1 subject-verb agreement**
 - 1.5.2 sentence fragment**
 - 1.5.3 run-on sentences**
 - 1.5.4 capitalization**
 - 1.5.5 punctuation**

Table 1 presents the frequency of errors for each category found in the written compositions of the TVL-ALGCIT Grade 11 students. The findings show that among the nine errors identified, students mostly make errors in punctuation with a total of 184 errors (17.60%) from the collected written compositions. This was followed by substitution errors with 178 errors (17.02%) among the collected compositions. On the other hand, the least number of errors made by the students in their compositions is on sentence fragment with 57 errors (5.45%). This was followed by errors in run-on sentences with 80 errors (7.65%) among the 45 written compositions. This is similar to the findings of Baguhin (2025), Arsate et al. (2025), and Blanco et al. (2025) where they analyzed the linguistic errors of college and high school students and found that the most number of errors was on punctuation. This is, however, in relation to linguistic errors made by the participants' written compositions. Meanwhile, in terms of surface strategy errors, substitution ranked highest in this study, similar to the studies of Setiyorini et al (2020), Arsate et al (2025) and Blanco et al. (2025). All these imply that the senior high school TVL-ALGCIT students are writing essays that lack clarity and precision as it makes the composition unclear or incomplete.

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage of the Grammar Errors of the Participants' Narrative-Descriptive Compositions

Type of error	Frequency	Percentage
Punctuation	184	17.60
Substitution	178	17.02
Omission	149	14.24
Addition	114	10.90
Permutation	97	9.27
Subject-verb agreement	97	9.27
Capitalization	90	8.60
Run on sentence	80	7.65
Sentence fragment	57	5.45
Total	1046	100.00

Punctuation errors

Punctuation marks in a sentence allow the writer to appropriately convey his or her message to the reader (Arquiola, et al. 2022). When errors in punctuation occur, readers become distracted from the meaning of the sentence or the essay, as the writing becomes

unclear, and its meaning may even be different from what it intends to convey. The whole composition may even become one whole run-on sentence. Examples of this error are demonstrated in the participants' written compositions:

(Composition #37) That time i wish to God that give another chances my dad still live, now I turning next year at My Legal Age i wish God's give me a chance that I can dance my father at my Special day.

(Composition #12) This song is the only song I relate the most, it helps me be calm and it let all the struggles get away.

(Composition #47) Where I can tell that I've tried and that's enough.

The excerpt of the first essay exhibits several punctuation errors. The sentence lacks both a comma and a period. The phrase "That time i wish" lacks a comma between "time" and "i" to emphasize the time the writer wanted something. This same sentence also consists of two clauses that must be separated by a period. Therefore, instead of a comma from the phrase "my dad still live, now I turning" a period is more appropriate. A period is placed at the end of a complete sentence while a comma indicates a short pause but not a complete stop of an idea (Kaufman & Straus, 2021).

In the second example, the comma in the phrase "I relate the most, it helps me" is not appropriate when separating the clauses. Instead of a comma, it should be replaced with a semicolon. Semicolons signal a pause that is slightly longer than that of a comma, but unlike the full stop that a period is used for (Kaufman & Straus 2021).

Meanwhile, the third example is a sentence fragment but ends with a period, thus giving the impression that it is a complete sentence. A complete sentence requires a subject and a predicate (Kaufman & Straus, 2021). In this example, only the predicate is present.

Substitution errors

Substitution refers to replacing a word to an incorrect word or form of a word in a sentence (Setiyorini, et al. 2020). This happens when a writer replaces a word, phrase, or grammar structure with an incorrect word, phrase, or grammar structure. Errors in substitution are demonstrated in the examples below:

(Composition #22). Story of my life by one direction because every people in this world have there own deferent kind...

(Composition #42) She was rushed to hospice and she been there for only 3days because she was being mercy killing, without our constent.

(Composition #32) But just like in the song I stand up strait and face the consequences of the wrong doings that I made.

The underlined words in the above sentences are examples identified as substitution errors. In the first essay, the word “people” should be changed to “person” since it follows a determiner “every” which indicates singular in number (Ba, 2026). In addition, in the same sentence, the words “have there own deferent” three of these words have been substituted making the error of incorrectly spelling the words. Since the determiner in the sentence is singular, the word “have” should also be in its singular form of “has”. The word “there”, which is an adverb of place, is not the correct word to be used, and since the writer speaks about a singular person, the more appropriate word to use would be the possessive adjectives “his” or “her”. Another substitution error in the same essay, which is done twice, is the misspelled word “deferent”, which should be spelled as “different”.

In the second example, the phrase “being mercy killing” and “constent” are identified as substitution errors. The use of the phrase “being mercy killing” could have been better written. The word “being” should have been removed while the word “euthanasia” would have been more appropriate than the phrase “mercy killing”. The next error is the word “constent” where the word “consent” is more appropriate.

The substitution error in the third example is manifested in the word “strait”, which refers to a narrow passage of water connecting two other large areas of water, where the sentence calls for the word “straight”.

Omission errors

Omission refers to letters or words that are absent in the sentence. This absence disrupts both the structure of the sentence and even the formation of the word or phrase. This involves absence in articles, prepositions, punctuations, nouns, pronouns or verbs within the written text (Gildore et al., 2023). Errors in omission are demonstrated in Table 1 with 185 errors (14.36%).

Composition #52. Through a world that full of challenges keep dreamin and be a star that symbolize who you trully are.

Composition #43. So I wrote this essay, Why if you heare the music “Not Afraid” By Eminem then you understand the music it’s so sad when you understand.

Composition #33. Life sometimes is painful and a lot of lesson, we feel pain...

The first example has several errors in omission. The phrase “Through a world that full of challenges keep dreamin” has missing items. The phrase “world that full” is missing the be verb “is” between “that” and “full” to describe the world. In the next phrase “challenges keep dreamin” is lacking a comma between “challenges” and “keep”, that will allow the reader to pause and know that an additional idea has been added. The letter “g” is also missing from the word “dreaming”. Lastly, the letter “s” is missing from the verb “symbolize” for it to be more appropriate in form to match the singular subject “star”.

The omission errors from the second example include omission of linking verbs, prepositions, punctuations, and missing letters. The first error the phrase “essay, Why if you”, a question mark after the word “Why” is missing. The writer here is asking a question on why he chose the song. The next phrase should be the beginning of the answer to the question on choosing the song. Another missing punctuation should be placed after the name of the singer “Eminem” from the phrase “music “Not Afraid” By Eminem then” to indicate the song of choice, before further explaining the reason for choosing the song.

Lastly, in the third example the phrase lacks the verb “has” to be placed between the words “and” and “a”. “Has” is a singular present tense form of “have” and is used to indicate possession of something (Kaufman & Straus 2021); in this case “life” is possessing something.

Addition errors

Addition refers to adding an unnecessary word in a sentence or a letter to a word, thus making the whole statement confusing in its message. Errors in addition are demonstrated in Table 4 with 146 errors (11.34%). The essays below demonstrate the addition errors found in the written compositions of the participants.

Composition # 58. This experience of me made me realized that no matter what happened when you are with your brother, the game will be easier and much safier.

Composition #26. The song that I’m choosing of, is the magdalenaby Freddie Aguilar.

Composition #49. In another life I will be always choose them.

The first error in the first example is the added phrase “of me” where it does not add clarity to the meaning of the sentence; rather it adds confusion to the reader. Another error in addition is from the word “safer” from the phrase “easier and much safier.”

The addition error of the second sentence is the preposition “of” and the comma after it from the first sentence “choosing of, is”. The other error in this sentence is the added article “the” before the title of the song.

Meanwhile, the addition error in the third sentence is the unnecessary addition of the word “be”. The use of the linking word “be” in this sentence is incorrect since it introduces a simple verb “choose” instead of introducing a gerund.

Permutation errors

Permutation refers to a word or phrase that is incorrectly placed in a sentence. This error also includes letters in a word that have been interchanged. This means that the elements in a sentence are jumbled, thus confusing the logical flow of the meaning (Blanco et al.

2025). Additionally, it disrupts standard subject-verb-object word order of the English grammar rules (Garcia & Amado, 2025). Errors in permutation are demonstrated in 97 errors (9.27%). The examples below show these errors.

Composition #56. The song that I can relate my life story is the song of one direction is about someone parting away from a group or simple this song is a goodbye song for someone.

Composition # 52. The song that really difine as a journey and describing who am I is the song of the movie “starlight”, because this song “I’m a shooting star” describe that I can do every I dream, even if there are so many obstacle in my life that who made me strong to face the challenge of life.

Composition #53. Like me, I used to be a star, shining, and active academically and in life.

This first example has the main clause of the sentence “my life story is the song” awkwardly follows the relative clause “that I can relate my life story”, creating a run-on with repeated “the song”. In order to correct it, the phrase should be written as “The song that I can relate to my life story is by One Direction...”

The second example has the permutation error of “describing who am I” which is formulated as a question, when in fact, the writer is simply stating a fact. As such it should be written as “describing who I am I”.

This third example has the introductory phrase “Like me” which makes the sentence confusing and its meaning vague. The writer should add an additional phrase in order to remove the confusion.

Subject-verb agreement

Errors involving a disagreement between a subject and its verb occur when the verb form does not match the subject in its number. The basic rule in the agreement between a subject and its verb is that a singular subject has to have a singular verb and a plural subject has to have a plural verb (Kaufman & Straus 2021). Instances that these errors occur in the written compositions of the participants are enumerated below:

Composition # 51. Furthermore, worship songs makes my heart at peace, that it feels like a surrender of every lyrics that speaks to me.

Composition #52. This symbolize and describe who am I, even if in my downs and up I keep dreamin and follow my heart for what it is desire, to achieve my goal in life this soundtrack keep me motivated as it is mysong in life.

Composition #63. These lyrics is the compass of my life, where there are

sure instances...

The examples above contain errors in the subject-verb agreement where the subjects are in plural form but the verb is singular form and the subject is singular but verbs used are in the plural form, thus the disagreement between the subject and its verb. The first one has the subject “worship songs” but the subject is followed by a singular verb “makes”. In the second example, the singular subject “This” is followed by plural verbs “symbolize” and “describe”. Similarly in the same sentence, another subject “soundtrack” is also followed by a plural verb “keep”. The third example uses the singular verb while referring to a plural subject.

Capitalization

Capitalization of letters in English grammar uses uppercase letters for specific words to signal importance, structure, or proper names, thus enhancing readability and serving as signals to the reader. Moreover, the rules on capitalization of letters vary but there are common rules that writers follow. These include the first word in a sentence, the pronoun “I”, and proper nouns, and titles of books, positions, and specific course titles (Maharani & Sholikhatun, 2022; Kaufman & Straus, 2021). Errors in capitalization occurs when the writer fails to write in capital letters the beginning of sentences, the pronoun “I”, or they fail to write in capital letters the proper nouns. Examples of this error can be seen in the written compositions of the grade 11 students

Composition #45. Some taught me lessons that i still carry even now, habits that i've adapted, things and places that they've introduced which became my favorite.

Composition #26. The song that I'm choosing of, is the magdalenaby Freddie Aguilar.

Composition #61. ...for the song writter which is Ed sheeran he wrote this music...

In the first example, the pronoun “I” is written in lowercase letter, when it should be otherwise. This includes writing the pronoun “I” as well as writing them in word contractions such as “i've”.

The second and third examples contain an error in the correct writing of the song title written as “magdalena” and the name of the song writer “Ed sheeran” which are written in lowercase letters when they are proper nouns.

Run-on sentence

A run-on sentence occurs when two or more independent clauses are joined together into one sentence but without proper connecting words or punctuations. Run-on sentences are also seen in the written compositions of the participants as presented below:

Composition #43. So I wrote this essay, Why if you hear the music "Not Afraid" By Eminem then you understand the music it's so sad when you understand.

Composition #13. Music can heal you specially when you are in the situation that feel so down or you are in your depression, because depression is not so easy to fight, depression can give harm in your life and this cannot give you a healthy life but when you try to listen to a music and let music heal you and forget all your problem and this can help you to feel comfort.

Composition #61. The meaning of this song for me is to fight over your depression, but for the song writer which is Ed sheeran he wrote this music for his mother/grand mother and play it in her funeral.

These three examples have too many ideas packed into one sentence, thus making it a run-on sentence. In addition, they lack appropriate connectors and appropriate punctuations. In both examples, there are several independent clauses that have been merged together to become one sentence. This demonstrates an incorrect sequence of clauses according to the Surface Strategy Taxonomy (Dulay, et al. 1982). In the first example, the second sentence is a run-on sentence; there are three clauses that have been merged into one without any proper punctuation.

Sentence fragment

Sentence fragments are incomplete sentences that lack a subject, a verb, or a complete thought, making them unable to stand by itself. Sentence fragment errors occur when a supposed sentence does not contain a subject or a verb. It can also occur when a dependent clause or phrase has an incomplete idea. Examples of this type of error are also found in the written compositions of the participants:

Composition #2. Because it tells and shows the story of someones life, from when a person is born up until he/she grows and being an adult.

Composition #34. Which is the music, were (d) make felt always free, gaving me a peace of mind and somewhere this music is also my healing treat.

Composition #53. The constant change that I am experiencing as I grow up.

In the above examples, the sentences are actually sentence fragments since they do not have a real subject. The subjects can be found in the previous sentence. However, because of the period placed at the end of the first sentence, these sentences have turned into sentence fragments that only contains a predicate.

The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of Baguhin (2025), Arsate et al. (2025), and Blanco et al. (2025) where they analyzed the linguistic errors of college and high school students and found that the most number of errors was on punctuation. Furthermore, the findings of this study matches those of Setiyorini et al (2020) and that of Blanco et al's (2025) where the highest number of surface strategy errors were those of substitution, followed by omission, then addition, and lastly was permutation. In a study by Uka et al (2023) it was stated that inadequate knowledge in the English language allows students to use words incorrectly. Additionally, when students replace words with incorrect ones, it will have an impact on the clarity of their written compositions (Baguhin, 2025).

Omission errors on the other hand, occur when letters or words are accidentally or purposely not written in the composition. This error occurs when students are unaware that they have omitted something in the sentence, thus showing carelessness in writing (Uka et al., 2023). Errors in addition ranked fourth highest in frequency. Errors in addition also affect the clarity and effectiveness of the written essay as it contains unnecessary words, thus meaning becomes more difficult (Arsate et al., 2025). Errors in permutation, which occurs when students have not mastered how to properly structure a sentence, produces inefficient writing (Uka et al., 2023). Sarasua's study however, found that errors in the agreement between subject and verb had the highest number of errors among the essays that were studied (2021) which contrasts this current study as this particular error ranked low among the identified errors. With all these errors, other researchers are in agreement that these errors occur because of unawareness and non-mastery of the rules of the English grammar, thus making their writing confusing and incomprehensible at times.

Research Question 2. Based on the findings of the study, what revised enrichment program can be recommended?

The TVL-ALGCIT Enrichment program lasts for 10 days during the month before the start of the new school year. These enrichment sessions include subjects on English, Mathematics, and Science. Each subject is allotted six hours in one week. The students will meet their Enrichment instructor for three hours in one day, twice a week. Based on the findings of the study, the enrichment lessons in English should focus on the following topics. Moreover, Table 2 presents the findings of the study in terms of the surface and linguistic errors, the list of topics or lessons to focus on, the suggested strategy to use in delivering the lesson, the time of which the lesson should be delivered, and the evaluation that will be given to the learners.

Table 2 Recommended Revised Enrichment Program in English for TVL-ALGCIT Students

The Revised Enrichment Program in English for TVL-ALGCIT Students was developed to provide a structured, research-based support for incoming Grade 11 TVL-ALGCIT students who require additional guidance in mastering concepts in the English grammar. This program's design follows a carefully sequenced order of lessons grounded on

educational research, ensuring that instruction is not only systematic but also responsive to the learning needs of the students. Furthermore, the program offers an intervention that is research-driven with activities that are learner-centered and cultivates mastery, confidence and long-term academic growth.

Research Finding	Lesson Implementation Plan	Activity and Evaluation
Punctuation and Capitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At the end of the session, students should be able to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ explain the rules for using a specific punctuation. ▪ identify words that need to be in uppercase form ▪ edit short passages by inserting appropriate punctuation marks and capitalization ▪ compose a short paragraph with accurate punctuation marks ▪ demonstrate attentiveness to detail by checking the punctuations and capitalization in their own written composition • Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Period ○ Comma ○ Apostrophe ○ Semi colon ○ Colon ○ Proper nouns ○ Pronoun "I" • Suggested strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reading aloud, pausing at punctuations ○ Capitalization hunt • Schedule: Week 1, Day 1, 3 hours 	<p>Activity: Pair work: Editing each other's sentences</p> <p>Evaluation: Checklist on proper use of punctuations and capitalizations</p>
Subject-verb agreement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At the end of the session, students should be able to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ identify the correct form of verb that matches the number of the subject ▪ correct sentences with errors in subject-verb agreement ▪ compose short paragraphs that demonstrate proper subject- 	<p>Activity: Writing a paragraph</p> <p>Evaluation: Rubric on correct application of subject-verb agreement</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> verb agreement, punctuation, and capitalization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ demonstrate attentiveness to correct grammar in their own written compositions • Topics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Nouns ○ Verbs ○ Pronouns • Suggested strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Matching games ○ Error hunts • Schedule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Week 1, Day 2, 3 hours 	
Run on sentence and sentence fragment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At the end of the session, students should be able to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ differentiate between a run-on sentence and a sentence fragment. ▪ edit and compose paragraphs that do not show either run-on sentences or sentence fragments. ▪ demonstrate attentiveness to sentence structure when writing • Topics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sentences ○ Punctuations • Suggested strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Matching games ○ Conjunction hunt • Schedule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Week 2, Day 1, 3 hours 	<p>Activity: Create a grammar infographic</p> <p>Evaluation: Rubric on infographic content</p>
Substitution, Omission, Addition, and Permutation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning Outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At the end of the session, students should be able to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ identify words or phrases that have been substituted, omitted, added, or rearranged with inappropriate words or word order ▪ Students will apply the appropriate words to the sentences ▪ demonstrate attentiveness to sentence structure when writing • Topics 	<p>Activity: Sentence transformation task</p> <p>Evaluation: Rubric checking the appropriateness of the word used</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Synonyms ○ Antonyms • Suggested strategies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strategy relay • Schedule <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Week 2, Day 2, 3 hours 	
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This order of the lessons will address the errors identified in this study according to the most number of errors to the least number of errors made by the participants. Moreover, this order of lessons ensures progressive mastery wherein the students will start from word or phrase lessons followed by sentence construction lessons that will then apply the previous lessons on word and punctuation mastery.

The lesson on punctuation needs to be tackled first since it is the linguistic error that has the highest frequency of being made by the students. The specific lessons will focus on the usual errors of incorrect use or not placing the appropriate punctuation on the written sentences. The suggested strategies in delivering the lessons in punctuation is reading aloud sentences and paragraphs and checking when to pause or stop, based on the punctuation. This session will also be joined by the lesson on capitalization, which will specifically tackle proper nouns and the pronoun “I”. A pair work editing activity can be used to evaluate the students’ progress on these two topics. The activity will allow students to check on each other’s learning.

The specific lessons for subject-verb agreement will focus more on nouns, verbs, and pronouns, specifically on their number, whether they are plural or singular in number. Matching games and hunting for errors in the sentences or paragraphs are the suggested strategies for delivering the lessons. These activities will allow the learners to identify the correct and incorrect verbs to pair with the nouns and pronouns. This lesson will need to be done on the second hour of the first day of the enrichment days. To check on the students’ progress, the teacher can have the students write a short essay on a provided topic, thus allowing the students to apply what they have learned and for the teacher to check on the students’ learning.

In the second week, the enrichment session can begin with lessons on run-on sentences and sentence fragments. Matching games and conjunction hunts can be used as strategies to allow the students to identify a run-on or sentence fragment and correct the error in the sentence by placing the appropriate punctuation or by breaking clauses into appropriate segments. This can be done for the entire duration of the session on the first day. The teacher can assess the students by having them create a grammar infographic about the lesson. In this way, the students themselves can create their own grammar guide explaining sentence fragments and run-on sentences with examples.

During the second meeting in the second week, the teacher can then begin an activity targeting the topics of substitution, omission, addition, and permutation. Specifically, the lesson will focus on synonyms and antonyms of words. This lesson is appropriate as it will allow the learners to know the appropriate word to use in delivering their intended

meaning. For this last session, the teacher can assign the students with a sentence transformation task where students are given a sentence to work on by identifying whether a word or phrase has been substituted, added, omitted, or incorrectly arranged.

These suggested strategies veer away from the traditional way of teaching grammar where the teacher gives the grammar rules and expect the students to memorize and recall such rules. These strategies allow the students to focus on the application of grammar rules in various exercises instead of simply memorizing the rules, thus improving the learner's self-esteem in learning English grammar (Ajaj, 2022).

Conclusions

Guided by Corder's Error Analysis Framework, the study examined the written compositions of Grade 11 TVL-ALGCIT students and identified grammatical difficulties manifested through mechanical inaccuracies and patterns associated with surface strategy taxonomy. Following the stages of error analysis—data collection, identification and description of errors, and evaluation—the analysis provided a diagnostic basis for improving the English Enrichment Classes offered to incoming students prior to their formal entry into the track. The findings show that students display a low proficiency in basic grammar, as shown in the number of grammar errors made, both with surface strategy and linguistic errors. These findings suggest the need for an improved enrichment program for the English subject, that is designed to be learner-centered with activities that can help students review their previous grammar lessons, at the same time allow them to think critically and demonstrate attentiveness to detail.

Based on these observations, a two-week enhanced English Enrichment program is proposed to strengthen learners' grammatical competence. The intervention prioritizes the mechanical aspects of grammar and common structural error patterns through focused instructional activities. By aligning instructional strategies with learners' specific language difficulties, the revised enrichment program aims to transform the current approach into an evidence-based remediation that systematically addresses grammar weaknesses among incoming TVL-ALGCIT students.

However, the findings of this study should be interpreted within certain limitations. The analysis was confined to written compositions produced by a specific group of Grade 11 TVL-ALGCIT students in one institutional context, which may limit the generalizability of the results to other tracks, grade levels, or educational settings. In addition, the study focused primarily on grammatical and mechanical errors and did not examine other dimensions of writing proficiency such as discourse organization, rhetorical development, or content quality. Future studies may expand the scope by including larger and more diverse samples and by examining additional aspects of writing performance to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of learners' language development.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. For school administrators, that they implement the suggested revised enrichment program made through this research. Implementing the revised enrichment program that is evidence-based builds scaffolding and reinforces connections among the lessons and ensures mastery when applying the lessons.
2. For the students, that they may be actively aware about the grammar errors that are commonly made, thus they will be able to practice avoiding the identified errors through constant practice writing.
3. For the English teachers, they may incorporate the findings of this study into making the lessons for the English Enrichment Classes, as well as in other English subjects.
4. For future researchers, they may extend this study to include another aspect of the study such as the background of the students and causes of why the errors occur. They may also come up with a different form of intervention to address the grammar errors identified in this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors strictly adhered to ethical standards for research involving student participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants which were distributed prior to data collection to allow sufficient time for review and authorization. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study, the procedures for handling the data, and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without academic or disciplinary consequences.

Confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing all written compositions. Names, sections, and other identifying information were removed prior to analysis. The collected data were coded and stored securely and were accessible only to the researcher. The study was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Lourdes College, ensuring compliance with institutional and national ethical standards. Following this approval, the researchers requested permission from the Vice President for Basic Education of the chosen university, as well as the school's principal and the director of the TVL-ALGCIT to gather data from the chosen participants. Upon their approval, the participants and their class moderators, were then informed of the purpose, scope, and procedures of the study, and their informed consent were obtained prior to data gathering.

The ethical conduct of the research was guided by the principles of the Belmont Report (NCPHS, 1979): respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Respect for persons was observed by securing informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, and protecting participant anonymity.

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